

in 1% urea solution for 3 h at planting, g) treatment a + chlorpyrifos 0.02% seedling root dip for 12 h at planting, and h) control. Neem cake and carbofuran granules were applied in the nursery at 20 days after sowing (DS) and water was impounded until seedlings were pulled and planted at 27 DS.

The comparative efficacy of different treatments was rated by GM damage and the grain yield (see table).

The carbofuran nursery treatment + chlorpyrifos seedling root dip was superior to nursery treatments with carbofuran alone or a combination of carbofuran and neem cake for controlling GM and encouraging higher grain yield. Irrespective of the combination of nursery treatments, neither carbofuran alone nor in combina-

Effect of different treatments on GM damage and rice grain yield at 50 DT.^a

Treatment	Gall midge damage (%)	Productive tillers/hill	Grain yield (t/ha)
Carbofuran 1.25 kg ai/ha	35 c	5.4 b	2.7 d
Carbofuran + 500 kg NC/ha	34 c	5.4 b	2.6 d
Carbofuran + 1000 kg NC/ha	35 c	5.4 b	2.5 d
Carbofuran + 1500 kg NC/ha	41 c	5.3 b	2.9 c
Carbofuran + 2000 kg NC/ha	35 c	5.6 b	2.8 cd
Carbofuran + RD with chlorpyrifos 0.02% in 1% urea solution for 3 h at planting	22 b	6.8 a	3.8 b
Carbofuran + RD with chlorpyrifos 0.02% for 12 h at planting	8 a	6.9 a	4.0 a
Control	42 c	4.0 c	2.1 c

^aIn a column, data with common letters are not significantly different at 5% level. NC = neem cake, DT = days after transplanting, RD = root dip.

tion with neem cake, even at 2,000 kg neem cake/ha, affected GM. Nursery treatment with carbofuran at 1.25 kg ai/ha +

chlorpyrifos 0.02% seedling root dip for 12 h before planting provided best and most economic control. □

Characterization of the brown planthopper population on IR42 in North Sumatra, Indonesia

K. Sogawa, Djatnika Kilin, and Bhagiawati A. H., Indonesia-Japan Joint Programme on Food Crop Protection, Jalan Ragunan, P.O. Box 36 Pasarminggu, Jakarta, Indonesia

Rice resistance to brown planthopper (BPH) is an important component in the integrated management of BPH in Indonesia. However, new BPH biotypes that defeated resistance traits of some rice varieties have evolved.

Drastic shifts of BPH biotypes that have occurred in North Sumatra, a BPH epidemic area in Indonesia, have followed shifts in rice varieties planted. Biotype 2 developed in 1977 on IR26, which has the *bph 1* gene. Until 1981, that biotype was effectively suppressed by IR36, which has the *bph 2* gene. However, recently introduced IR42 with the *bph 2* gene was damaged by a new biotype.

We compared the BPH population collected from IR42 in North Sumatra (hereafter the N. S. population) with that of the known biotypes by two honeydew tests: one with filter paper and one with parafilm envelopes. The N. S. population was reared for about 20 successive generations on IR42 at the Bogor Food Crops Research Institute. Biotypes 1, 2, and 3 have been maintained as isolated inbred

Relative amounts of honeydew excreted by 4 BPH biotypes on 7 rice varieties, 1983.^a

Variety	Honeydew ^a			N.S. ^b
	Biotype 1	Biotype 2	Biotype 3	
TN1	19.0	18.5	17.7	10.2
Pelita I/1	21.8	15.6	16.5	10.4
IR26	3.8	14.9	2.6	4.1
Cisadane	±	±	4.8	3.6
IR42	±	±	3.6	11.1
IR36	±	±	±	2.1
IR56	±	±	±	±

^a Five adult females were confined on a plant at about 30 days after transplanting for 22 hours at room temperature. Values indicate the areas of water blue filter paper impregnated with honeydew in cm² (av of 3 replications). Excretion of only a small number of droplets is indicated by ±. ^bNorth Sumatra population.

populations on Pelita I/1, Mudgo, and ASD7, respectively, since 1977.

Table 1 shows estimates by the filter paper method of the relative amounts of honeydew excreted by adult females of the three biotypes and the N. S. on selected rice varieties. The N. S. population was differentiated from biotype 2 by a poor ability to feed on IR26, and from biotypes 1 and 3 by an improved ability to feed on IR42 (see table). N. S. feeding characteristics were further confirmed by the parafilm envelope method and compared to those of BPH biotype 3. The N. S. population excreted as much honeydew on *bph 2*-resistant varieties ASD7 and IR42 as on susceptible variety Pelita I/1, but excreted strikingly less honeydew on

Means and 95% confidential ranges of the amount of honeydew excreted by adult females of the N. S. population and biotype 3 at Bogor on 8 rice varieties at about 45 days after transplanting. About 20 insects were used for each variety, 1983.

Babawee, IR56, Mudgo, Cisadane, and IR36 (see figure). This indicated that the N. S. population belongs to biotype 3, which has specific ability to feed on *bph 2*-resistant varieties.

However, the N. S. population has a significantly higher ability to feed on IR42 than does biotype 3 at Bogor. N. S. insects excreted nearly 30 mg honeydew/female per d, while those from the biotype 3 culture excreted only 5 mg (see figure). These different BPH responses seem to indicate that there are different genetic factor(s) in each host variety that cause a distinct reaction to IR42 on each biotypic population, although IR42 and ASD7 have been said to possess the same *bph 2* gene. □